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ENHANCEMENT OF SECONDARY METABOLITE PRODUCTION IN ABRUS PRECATORIUS LINN. VIA GENETIC TRANSFORMATION

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ABSTRACT

Although *Glycyrrhiza glabra* is the recognized source of glycyrrhizin, its production in tissue culture has not been successful by tissue culture. *Abrus precatorius* is an alternative source for glycyrrhizin and was thus taken up in tissue culture technique for glycyrrhizin production. The yield enhancement for the glycyrrhizin production was done by means of genetic transformation using *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*. When compared with untransformed callus resulted in 8.665 ± 0.144 g/l dry cell weight biomass and $0.427 \pm 0.0016\%$ glycyrrhizin, which was 2.4-fold times higher in productivity in comparison to control untransformed cultures.

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INTRODUCTION

Plants produce bio-chemicals that are of importance in the healthcare, food, flavour and cosmetics industries. Many pharmaceuticals are produced from the secondary metabolites of plant. Often the source plants are cultivated in tropical or subtropical, geographically remote, areas which are subjected to political instability, drought, disease and changing land use patterns and other environmental factors. In addition, the long cultivation period between planting and harvesting make selection of high-yielding strains difficult. These factors have generated considerable interest in the use of plant cell culture technologies for the production of pharmaceuticals (Dicosmo *et al.*, 1990) and other plant derived bio-chemicals.

The plant cell culture technology is now sufficiently advanced to allow for large quantities of relatively homogeneous, undifferentiated cells to be produced. Plant cell and tissue culture systems are complementary and may provide competitive metabolites production systems when compared to whole plant extraction. Callus culture is formation of mass of cells in a solidified media, whereas cell suspension culture is cells suspended in liquid media. Large scale plant suspension cultures are expected to be suitable for industrial production of plant derived bio-chemicals,

Secondary metabolism is the synthesis and metabolism of endogenous compounds by specialized proteins (Luckner *et al.*, 1977). The results of these processes are secondary metabolic products. They are an expression of cell specialization which is either triggered by the process of cell differentiation (Luckner *et al.*, 1977) or represents an aspect process of plant development.

Agrobacterium mediated genetic transformation is the dominant technology used for the production of genetically modified transgenic plants. *Agrobacterium* genetically transforms its host by transferring a well defined DNA segment from its tumor-inducing (Ti) plasmid to the host-cell genome (Gelvin *et al.*, 1998). In nature, the transferred DNA (T-DNA) carries a set of oncogenes (Gaudin *et al.*, 1994) and opine-catabolism genes, the expression of which, in plant cell, lead to neoplastic growth of the transformed tissue and the production of opines, amino acid derivatives used almost exclusively by the bacteria as a nitrogen source.

Abrus precatorius is used as abortifacient, antidote, aphrodisiac, con-traceptive, anti-diuretic, emetic, and also in the treatment of convulsion, cough, diarrhea, gingivitis, gonorrhoea, hook-worms, jaundice, ophthalmic disease, rheumatism, trachoma, vermifuge, etc. (Jackinovich *et al.* 1990; Nwodo 1991; Ratnasooriya *et al.* 1991; Molgaard *et al.* 2001). *Abrus* is possibly native of Indian, Africa (Neal, 1965) and most of the tropics (Acevedo-Rodriguez, 1985).

Previous workers have claimed that glycyrrhizin is the sweet principle of *A. precatorius* leaves (Hooper, 1894; Anonymous, 1985; Irvine, 1961; Akinloye and Adalumo, 1981) According to some literature the roots contain higher percentage of glycyrrhizin (Dymock, 1890; Hooper, 1894; Anonymous, 1985; Inglett and May, 1968) than leaves. Chemically, glycyrrhizin is a triterpenoid glycosidic saponin present in roots and rhizome of Licorice plant *Glycyrrhiza glabra* and roots and leaves of *A. precatorius* (Wild licorice or Indian licorice). The crude dried aqueous extract 4-25% (also known as black licorice) may contain glycyrrhizic acid in the form of calcium, magnesium and potassium salt. Glycyrrhizin, which consists in the calcium and potassium salts of glycyrrhizic acid (Glycyrrhizic acid) is converted upon hydrolysis into the aglycone glycyrrhetic acid (glycyrrhetic acid) plus two molecules of glucouronic acid. The acid form is not particularly water-soluble, but its ammonium salt is soluble in water at pH greater than 4.5.

Present investigations were undertaken with a view to enhance production of glycyrrhizin in *abrus precatorius* utilizing tissue culture techniques like genetic transformation. Glycyrrhizin is a phytoconstituent of importance for the pharmaceutical and food industry. Glycyrrhizin used as hepatoprotective, immunomodulator, Anti HIV, expectorant, flavoring agent/ sweetener, antitumor, anti-inflammatory agent etc. Thus it is of prime important plant constituent of medicinal values and our aim was to establish a protocol/ procedure for its enhanced production by tissue culture techniques.

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

Collection of seeds

Seeds of *Abrus precatorius* were collected from medicinal plant garden, Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Dr. H. S. Gour University Sagar, M. P. with identification no. Bot. / H / 5865.

Aseptic germination of seeds

The viable seeds were taken in a culture tube (slightly tilted position) and washed under running tap water. The seeds were surface sterilized by 70% ethanol for 1-2 min, then with sodium hypochlorite (4%) for 10-12 min and then rinsed 7-8 times with sterilized double distilled water. Now the sterile seeds were aseptically germinated at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ at 12-12 h photoperiod at normal humidity conditions. The germination of seeds of *Abrus precatorius* started at 8th day, 90% germination was observed at 12th day, after 14th day germinated seed had two distinct cotyledons. Finally the grown seedlings were aseptically transferred to sterile 250 ml conical flask for further growth.

Initiation and Maintenance of Callus Culture

Explants from aseptically germinated plantlets were aseptically transferred with sterile forceps to a solid (0.8% agar) MS medium with each with proper and combination of cytokinin and auxin hormones in a petri-dish and 250 ml conical flask. These were incubated at $25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ on the solid MS medium in dark for initial seven days till callus induction started. After callus induction the culture plates were incubated under 12/12 hr light/dark cycle and at light regimens ranging from 1500-2500 lux provided by fluorescent tubes. Among the various plant growth regulators attempted the NAA (1mg/l) + kinetin (1mg/l) was the best optimized concentration for the induction and growth of calli of *Abrus precatorius* explants. After ten days compact, friable creamy whitish colored callus induced in leaf explant on NAA (1mg/l) + kinetin (1mg/l) with 65% callogenesis. Callus cultures were maintained by sub culturing regularly at interval of every three weeks on the fresh medium. It was maintained at the same hormonal concentration, which was best for callus initiation of *Abrus precatorius* explant during subsequent sub-culturing.

Effect of hormonal concentration on *Abrus precatorius* Leaf explants

Hormonal concentration	Days after which callus initiation starts	Callus characteristics	% callogenesis
2,4-D (1mg/l)	14-16	Creamish coloured Callus	20%
NAA (1mg/l)	-	-	0
Kn (1mg/l)	-	-	0
NAA (1mg/l) + Kn (1mg/l)	10-12	Friable creamy whitish coloured	65%
NAA (1mg/l) + BAP (2mg/l)	13-15	Compact pale coloured	40%
2,4-D(1mg/l)+ BAP (2mg/l)	16-18	Compact pale coloured	25%

A total of 20 explants were taken for each observation; each experiment performed in triplicate (n=3).

Callus growth determination

Suspension cultures were initiated by aseptic transfer of friable fraction of callus equivalent to 1 to 1.5 g/l fresh cell weight into 250 ml Erlenmeyer flask containing 50 ml of liquid MS medium. The plant hormones added were NAA + Kn 1mg/l each. Culture were incubated on a gyratory shaker at 110±10 rpm at 25±1°C under 12/12 h light/dark regime. The suspension culture was maintained in MS medium containing NAA (0.5mg/l) and Kn (0.5 mg/l) without agar and subcultured at an interval of two weeks at 25±1°C and 110±10 rpm.

Determination of Glycyrrhizin

(a) Qualitative estimation was performed by TLC with solvent system Toluene: ethyl acetate: glacial acetic acid (12.5:7.5:0.5) (Chauhan et al., 1998)

(b) Quantitative estimation was performed by HPLC (Killacky et al., 1976) on Shimadzu (Integration: Hewlett Packard) HPLC with photodiode array detector, SPD-10 MA system, glycyrrhizin was separated on Phenomenex (250x4.6 mm) RP₁₈ 5µ column. Methanol: water (70: 30) Isocratic solvent was used for estimation of glycyrrhizin as its hydrolysis product 18-β-glycyrrhetic acid.

Glycyrrhetic acid (GA) content in suspension culture of *Abrus precatorius*.

S.No.	Culture age (days)	Culture Biomass (g L ⁻¹ DW)	%Glycyrrhetic acid content
1	5	1.005±0.31	0.0032±0.0022
2	10	2.837±0.27	0.0057±0.0034
3	15	4.605±0.61	0.089±0.0012
4	20	5.456±0.11	0.105±0.0038
5	25	5.304±0.40	0.097±0.0024
6	30	4.322±0.38	0.058±0.0025

Results were mean ± SD of triplicate samples.

Transformed Callus Culture

In the present investigation *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* NCIM 2943 was used to establish *Abrus precatorius* transformed cell culture. *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* (NCIM 2943) was obtained from National Collection of Industrial Microorganisms (NCIM) Pune. *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* NCIM 2943 was maintained in YEB media and subcultured at regular interval of 30 days. Culture of bacterial strain was maintained at 26°C.

Optimization of various conditions for the establishment of transformed callus culture of *Abrus precatorius* explants

Effect of Media on Transformed Callus Culture.

S. No.	Transformation experimental conditions	Characteristics	Days after Callusing starts	Intensity of formed callus	% *Transformation Efficiency
1	MS-Media	Unorganized friable callus	4-5	++++	80%
2	GB-5 Media	Soft Callus mass of Cream colour	6-7	++	65%

Effect of pH on Transformed Callus culture.

1.	pH 4.5±0.3	Tissue necrosis	--	---	----
2.	pH 5.5±0.3	Compact Callus mass	5	++	68%
3.	pH 6.5±0.3	Soft friable growth	4-5	++++	72.2%
4.	pH 7.5±0.3	Loose callus mass	6	+++	70%

Effect of Density of Bacterial inoculums.

1.	0.50 (OD ₆₀₀)	Low growth	6-7	++	52.11%
2.	1.00 (OD ₆₀₀)	Best callus growth	4-5	++++	61%
3.	1.50 (OD ₆₀₀)	Good callus	5-6	+++	59%

Effect of Infection time of Inoculum.

1.	15 min.	low callus growth	6	++	59%
2.	30 min.	best callus growth	5	+++	55%
3.	45 min.	Good gall formation	4	+++	43.2%

Effect of concentration of Acetosyringone.

1.	0 µM	Whitish Callus formed	5-6	+++	67.2% %
2.	50 µM	Good gall formation	4-5	++++	73.3%
3.	100 µM	Profusely grown gall	4-5	++++	78%

Each experiment was done in duplicate with ten explants per treatment

*Percentage Transformation Efficiency calculated on the basis of opine positive crown gall culture.

Confirmation of Transformed cells

The transformation conformation was done by opine assay using Electrophoresis (*Petit et al., 1983*) 64% transformation efficiency was found.

Initiation of Transformed Cell Suspension Cultures of *Abrus precatorius*

Suspension cultures were initiated by aseptic transfer of friable fraction of callus equivalent to 0.5 to 1.0 g fresh cell weight into 250 ml Erlenmeyer flask containing 50 ml of liquid Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium without any growth hormone. Cultures were incubated on a gyratory shaker at 110 rpm at 25 ± 1°C under 12/12 h light/ dark regime. The suspension culture was maintained in liquid MS medium without any plant growth hormone and subcultured at an interval of two weeks at 25±1°C and at 110 r.p.m under 12/12 h light/ dark regime.

Growth Parameters of Transformed Cell Suspension Culture of *Abrus precatorius*

Culture Period (Days)	*Mean Fresh Weight (g)	*Mean Dry Weight (mg)	% Biomass Increase (FW)
5	0.118±0.06	16.29±2.14	290%
10	1.236±0.41	29.56±3.27	398%
15	3.005±0.44	78.21±3.21	487%
20	5.723±0.64	108.00±2.42	580%
25	4.995±0.57	72.22±1.00	560%
30	4.977±0.20	52.33±2.08	501%

*Results were mean ± SD of triplicate sample

Glycyrrhetic acid (GA) content in transformed suspension culture of *Abrus precatorius*.

Culture period (Days)	Culture biomass (g ^L ⁻¹ DW)*	Glycyrrhetic acid content (% DW)*
0	-	-
5	1.770±0.35	0.0041±0.0025
10	3.772±0.168	0.099±0.0013
15	6.642±0.102	0.286±0.0042
20	8.665±0.144	0.427±0.0016
25	7.994±0.22	0.402±0.0030
30	5.148±0.186	0.301±0.0012

*Results were mean ± SD of triplicate samples.

CONCLUSION AND RESULTS

When compared untransformed callus culture with transformed callus culture, give increase in GA content. *A. tumefaciens* transformed cultures of *A. precatorius* were successfully induced from *in vitro* grown plants with 64% transformation efficiency. Complete growth, production of *A. precatorius* cells in the suspension culture were established. Maximum biomass (8.665±0.144g/Ldry weight) and Glycyrrhetic acid accumulation (0.427±0.0016% DW) were obtained on the 20 th day of cultivation. This study represents a successful approach for the production of Glycyrrhetic acid content by transformed cell suspension cultures from *A. precatorius*. Significantly higher Glycyrrhetic acid content accumulation was obtained in comparison to that reported earlier. This yield enhancement could generally be applied for the development of cell culture-based bioprocesses for mass-scale production of commercially important phytochemicals. Further research work in this direction is under progress.

REFERENCES

- Addicott T, Along, R Abscission, Berkeley: Univesity of California press 1995 ; 2; 531-546
- Adel A, Al-Alousi L, Hatem A AAPS PharmSciTech. 2004.
- Agrawal S, Ghatak N, Arora R and Bhardwaj M. Pharmacological Research Communications 1970; 2(2): 159-163.
- Akinloye A , Adalumo L Niger J Pharm 1981;12(2); 405.
- Albert M , Denong W Lectins 2007; 167-192
- Arias C, Scragg H, Stafford A, Rodriguez M Plant cell, Tissue and organ culture 1993;34;77-82
- Baldi A , Dixit V Bioresource Technology 2008; 99(11); 211-213
- Basu, A. P. Indian Journal of Pharmacy 1993;35(6); 203
- Blume Y, Alla Y, Vladimir R, Oleg B, Galina B, Alexey P,et al. Cell Biology International; 2008; 32(5) 566-570
- Chan W, Staba J, Lloydia 1965 28,55
- Chaturvedi M. M.Pharm dissertation submitted to Dr. H.S.Gour University. Sagar. M.P ,2006
- Chauhan S,Singh B, Kimothi G, Agarwal S. Indian J of Pharmaceutical Sci. 1998; 60(4), 251-253.
- Chilton W, Hood E, Chilton M. Phytochemistry 1985;24,221–224.
- Chong T, Abdullah M, Lai O, Nor F, Lajis N. Proc. Biochem. 2005; 40; 3397-3405.
- Desai V and Sirsi M. Antimicrobial activity of *Abrus precatorius* Linn, Indian Journal of Pharmacy.1966;28;164-165
- Dhingra D, Parle M, Kulkarni S.Memory enhancing activity of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* in mice Journal of Ethnopharmacology.2004; 91; 361–365.
- DiCosmo F Misawa M. Eliciting secondary metabolism in plant cell cultures. Trends Biotechnol. 1985;3;318–322.

- 18.Ebel J, Mithofer A. *Planta*. 1998; 206; 335- 348.
- 19.Eilert U. Elicitation: methodology and aspects of application. In: Constabel F, Vasil I, editors. *Cell culture and somatic cell genetics of plants* San Diego: Academic Press.1987; 1; 153–196.
- 20.Engstrom P, Zambryski P, Montagu M., Stachel S. Characterization of *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* virulence proteins induced by the plant factor acetosyringone *Journal of Molecular Biology* .1987;197(4);635-645.
- 21.Escobar M,Dandekar A. *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* as an agent of disease. *Trends Plant Sci*. 2003; 8;380-386.
- 22.Evans . *Pharmacognosy* 14th edition, 4th reprint, Pub. By W. B. Saunders Company Ltd., London, 20011; 86;470-490.
- 23.Fujita Y. Industrial production of shikonin and berberine. *Applications of plant cell and tissue culture*. Ciba Foundation Symposium 137. Chichester: Wiley. 1988; 228–38.
- 24.Furuya T, Matsumoto K, Hikichi M. Echinatin.A new chalcone from tissue culture of *Glycyrrhiza echinata*. *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1971; 2567-9
- 25.Futerer J, Gisel A and Iglesias V In: Potrykus I and Spangenberg G. (Eds.), *Gene Transfer to plants*, Springer, Berlin, (1995);215.
- 26.Gaudin V, Vrain T, Jouanin L. Bacterial genes, modifying hormonal balances in plants. *Plant physiol Biochem* 1994;32;11.
- 27.Gelvin S. *Agrobacterium*-mediated plant transformation: the biology behind the ‘gene-jockeying’ tool. *Microbiol. Mol. Biol. Rev.* 2003; 67; 16–37.
- 28.Gengaihi E, Karawya M. Investigation of flavonoids of *Abrus precatorius*. *Herba Hungarica* 1988; 27(1); 27-34.
- 29.Hayashi H, Fufui H, Tabata M. *Plant Cell Rep*. 1988;7;508-511
- 30.Jain R. PhD. thesis submitted to Dr. H.S.Gour University. Sagar. M.P 2007
- 31.Killacky J., Ross M.S.F. and Turner T.D. *Planta Medica*. 1976; 30;310-316
- 32.Murashige T. and Skoog, F. *Physiol. Plant* 1962; 15;473
- 33.Ratnaparkhi N. (2004) M.Pharm dissertation submitted to Dr. H.S.Gour University. Sagar. M.P
- 34.Saxena V.K , Sharma D.N. (1999) *Fitoterapia* 70, 328-329
- 35.Shah, C.S. and Bhatta, J. G. (1973) *Indian Journal of Pharmacy* 35(3): 102-104.
- 36.Sharma S. (2007) M. Pharm Thesis, Dept. of Pharm. Sciences, Dr. H.S. Gour University, Sagar.
- 37.Singh V (2008) M. pharm Thesis, Dept. of Pharm. Sciences, Dr. H.S. Gour University, Sagar.
- 38.Sharma T and Dixit V.K. (2006) *Ind. J Pharm Sci*. 68 (4): 448.
- 39.Vyas, S.P. and Dixit, V.K. (1998). "Pharmaceutical Biotechnology", CBS Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi, 1st ed., p.237, 249.

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